

Code of Conduct of Nominee Director Through Different Legislation

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Abstract

This conceptual study explains that how to admit a Nominee Director and their role in Board. This paper thrash out about the Nominee director's independence and interest which carries towards the board, runs through different legislation.

Introduction

A financial Institution to wheedle on the Board of a Company, in exercise of its influencetogether with this in the terms and conditions attached generally with a solicit arrangement willowy by the company.

The legal requirement of LODR, the Stock Exchanges, a Nominee Director representing abody which has devote in or let somebody have provisionally to the company was considered as an "Independent Director". Section 149(6) of the Companies Act, 2013 states clearly that a Nominee director would not be considered as an Independent Director.

Under the aegis of Section 161(3),give power to the Board to employ a Nominee director. The concern rendezvous shall not call for regularization by the Shareholders of the company, in acquiescence with Section 160 of the Act, in the case of persons prearranged as Additional Directors, to fill up laid-back vacancies in the Board and similar to. In this elucidation, we shall chuck light on the above issues andconvey to the fore certain grey areas which need introspection.

Role of Nominee Director

Nominee Director –is not considered as Independent Director under the Act. Under Section 149(7) of the Act defines a "Nominee Director" as means a director nominated by any financial Institution in pursuance of the provisions of any law for the time being in force, or of any agreement, or appointed by any Government, or any other person to represent its interests".

The following are the traits:

- a) Selected by any financial Institution in pursuance of any law or in terms of an concurrence entered into by the company
- b) Agreed by the Government or by any other personality.
- c) Shall represent the welfare of the organization/Institution, which he symbolizes and should comply under Section 149(6) of the Act.

The JJ Irani have articulated the view that Nominee directors appointed by any Institution or in pursuance of any agreement or Government appointees on behalf of Government, should not be considered Independent director. In another point of view, nominees of Banks/Financial Institutions on the Board can be treated as “Independent”. The Committee concluded that such nominees who represent specific interest are termed as nominal directors and those who do not carry sort of specific interests rightly termed as Independent directors. The opinion expressed by the group have found place in the form of a declaration in Section 149(6) to the effect that Nominee directors must not to be considered as Independent directors. Discrepancy in the Act-Directors’ representing Small shareholders are Independent directors under Section 151 of the Act in the case of a listed company.

Nominee Director Vs Independent Director

The description “Small shareholders” mean shareholders holding shares of a nominal value not more than twenty thousand rupees or such other sum as might be prearranged. Rule 7 of the companies (Appointment and Qualification of directors) Rules, 2014 put down, inter alia, the procedure to be followed for the appointment of such a director. Rule 7(4) insist on that such director shall be considered as an Independent director, he is being eligible for the appointment in terms of Section 149(6) and subject to in accordance with the provisions of Section 149(7). A director elected by diminutive shareholders would be deemed an Independent director under Section 151 and it is incumbent upon him to protect the interest of his constituency. The JJ Irani committee had opined that as such nominee directors represented specific interests should not be deemed independent. The fact that the diminutive shareholders’ director too correspond to a specific interest group, he is well thought-out as an Independent director. The odd jobs of both classes of directors are impossible to tell apart; they should both stand on the same plinth. The Nominee Director retires by rotation even though, he is not an Independent Director.

Section 161(3) of the Act endow with that subject to the Articles of a company, the Board appoint any person as a Director designated by any Institution pursuant to law for the time being in force, or of any agreement or by the concern Government. The concern nominees have been appointed pursuant to any legal provision applicable to the financial Institution, nominating the person.

Those appointed under any statutory provisions in force, shall not be liable to retire by turning round under Section 152(6) and they shall continue to remain Directors as per the will and pleasure of the institutions put forward them in spite of not get pleasure from the status of Independent directors. The authority bestow under the previously mentioned legislations would have an superseding effect over the provisions in the Act, thus pays the way for the person to appoint as Nominee to continue in office at the will and pleasure of the Institution. Nominee director will also not be taken into consideration for determining the two-thirds and one-third limits as provided in Section 152 (6) of the Act.

A precondition to such a rendezvous would be the survival of enabling clause in the company’s Articles to ease such an appointment. It is relevant to note that Section 161(3) in the Act embark on with the words “Subject to the Articles of a company”. The words construct is clear that the appointment of a Nominee director in all state of affairs, be it through the force of a particular legislation or by concord.

In *James v Eve* (1873) LR 6 HL 335 held that the company’s articles make available for the appointment of directors by recommendation of shareholders at the general meeting, a indenture by which the company profess to confer the rights on any other person to make schedule to the Board in any other way is worthless. It is also possible that the nomination agreement among the members will also be in material form in the articles. The person empowered to make nominations in terms

of the agreement can exercise such authority as long as he is in the saddle and continues to hold authority under the agreement.

In *East Indian Produce Co. Ltd v Naresh Acharya Bhaduri* (1988) 64 Com Cases 259, 278 (Cal) The Court apprehended that the clause did not affect the provisions of Sections 255 and 256 of the 1956 Act prevailing rotation of directors. The Holding Company has the right to appoint majority of directors unswerving with Section 152 of the Act. The concern section commune to Section 255 and section 4 of the 1956 Act. The concern Section 2(87) of the 2013 Act, which confers on the Holding Company the right to control the symphony of the Board of the Subsidiary by which process the latter becomes a subsidiary even without the Holding company exercising control over more than half of the voting power in the company.

The Companies Act 2013- Appointment of Nominee Director under Section 161(3) "Subject to the articles of association of a company, the Board may appoint any person as a director nominated by any institution in pursuance of the provisions of any law, for the time being in force or of any agreement or by the concern Government in virtue of its shareholding pattern." The above quotation marks that the Articles of the company contain enabling clause, the Board can appoint as a Nominee director, who is nominated by any Institution or person or by the Government.

It is relevant to make a note of that Section 152(2) affirm as under:

"Save as otherwise expressly provided in the Act, every director shall be appointed by the company in general Meeting." Inference of the term "Save as otherwise expressly provided in this Act" which is mentioned under in Wharton's Law Lexicon: and which is reinstated in the case law (*Sambhu Nath Sarkar v State of West Bengal* (AIR 1973 SC 1425 (1973)).

Under Section 152(2) is that the company in general Meeting subject to exceptions as expressly provided in the Act shall appoint every director, is a general rule. Section 161 says the Board is empowered subject to the company's Articles, to appoint directors

1. Appointment of any person, who has not retired in General Meeting as Additional Director.
2. Appointment of a person who does not embrace any alternate directorship for any other director in the company, to act as an alternate director, for a director during his absence for a period of not less than three months from India.
3. Appointment any person as a director nominated by any Institution/ by any agreement as a Nominee director.
4. The public company to fill up a casual vacancy in the office of any director who has been appointed in general meeting and before the expiry of his term. The concern appointment has to be regularized in the general meeting with reference to Section 160.

The Alternate director's tenure automatically ends upon the return to office of the original director. The people who cling to office to fill up a casual vacancy will hold office until the conclusion of the term of the person whose void he has filled up. The Act is silent on the point whether the nominee director is liable to retire by rotation or not. The Act is silent on the issues affirmed above; one has to take a view that once the Board has a Nominee director, appointed the person is no requirement to seek approval of the shareholders.

Need for structuring Board as per Section 152(6) consequent upon appointment of Independent director as a Nominee director does not retire by rotation nor he is an Independent director. The appointment the company should ensure that the Board continues to remain structured in the manner weigh up under section 152(6). The listed companies, which are under obligation to appoint Independent directors under Section 149, should ensure that they continue to have the required number of Independent directors, even after a Nominee has been a member on the Board. The Nomination and Remuneration Committee have any part to play in the appointment of the Nominee Director (under Section 178), those companies which meet with the decisive factor

laid down in Rule 6 of the companies (Meetings of Board and its powers) Rules, 2014 have to constitute a Nomination and Remuneration Committee. Section 178(2) clearly state, the existing committee had to identify persons who are qualified to become directors, recommend to the Board for appointment.

The recommendation, which is made by the Committee, is a prior requirement for the appointment of any person as a director by the Board. However, in the case of nominee director, the committee has no role in fact to play, it purely lays on the Institution under a Statute or an agreement, the Committee simply follows the procedure. The above perception, obligation be stated that the provisions of Section 178 are not in harmony with Section 161(3). The Board's Role and appointment of Nominee Director as the Nominee involuntarily stands agreed through the influence of the Institution. The role of the board is only ornamental. The Board will have to ensure that the current endow with the director, for the appointment under Section 152(5), within thirty days from the date of appointment, form DIR 12 has to be filed. The Nominee director has to be furnished a declaration that he is not facing any disqualification or disqualified to become a director as per the inference under Section 152(4) and it is recorded in the Minutes. The company Secretary has to ensure that legal requirements and formalities are met in the appointment of the director.

The company have to intimate to Stock Exchange (in case of a listed company) as per requirement of Regulation 30 of the SEBI (Listing Obligations Disclosure Requirements - LODR) Regulations 2015, as soon as the appointment of a Nominee director, whether it falls in the line of agreement, which is specified by the institution. The insinuation should also point out the tenure of the appointment, if the nominating institution has stated that.

Conclusion

In the above exposition, we have tried to bring the core issues that emerge from the appointment of a Nominee Director. The Statute, as it stands, is not giving any clarity on the point as to whether a Nominee is liable to retire by rotation or whether his appointment is subject to regularization by the shareholders. Through this, there are lot of scope for interpretations and speculative conjectures on these issues. The role of the Nomination Committee and the Board also stands marginalized substantially in view of the provisions contained in Section 161(3). Besides, we have to live with the inherent contradiction that while a Nominee director is not an Independent director; a director for small shareholders is one. No law can ever be perfect, given that it is a creation of man. Our wish list would be endless for an ever-elusive law. Hence, we have to accept the reality of the Statute stoically and learn to grapple with its nuances.

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